

ARCHAEOLOGICAL EVIDENCE FOR SETTLEMENT IN SOUTHEASTERN IRAN

Southeastern Iran is geographically diverse and, although limited in water and arable land, is rich in non-subsistence resources. Except for the surveys of Sir Aurel Stein in 1915-1916 and 1931-1932, the area was little known archaeologically prior to 1960. Since then the excavations at Dahan-i-Ghulaman, Shahr-i-Sokhta, Bampūr, Tal-i-Iblīs, Shāhdād, and Tepe Yahyā have begun to provide the temporal and geographical framework of this large region.

Archaeological surface survey over the past two years has been undertaken by myself in conjunction with Andrew Williamson of the British Institute of Persian Studies and Oxford University. Although primarily concentrated on the Persian Gulf coast and focused on the Sassanian and Islamic material, this survey also covered a number of the major river valleys of the southeast, including among others: the Halīl Rūd, Rūd-i-Duzdī, Rūd-i-Rūdān, and Rūd-i-Jagin.

Pre-Sassanian settlement was generally dispersed, with rarely more than one settlement of a period in any area, even in those localities with perennial fluvial water and considerable Islamic or modern occupation. One of the few clusterings of pre-Sassanian settlement, of fifth and fourth millennia B.C. date and located on the Rūd-i-Gushk near Dolatābād in southern Kirmān, is the focus of current research on the patterns of settlement growth and distribution and the determinants of settlement location.

The available material from Stein's and other surveys will be synthesized with my own, as well as with other published and unpublished information on settlement in southeastern Iran. These will be placed in the chronological framework produced by the excavated sites of the region, primarily Tepe Yahyā. In spite of the as yet fragmentary nature of our knowledge of site distributions, considerable information on the patterns of settlement in southeastern Iran is becoming available.

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